

Project Number: 101005111
Project Acronym: DECISION
Project Title: A miniaturized disposable molecular diagnostics platform for combatting coronavirus infections

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

1. Data Summary

The DECISION Consortium is developing a new class of diagnostic system that will transform the fight against pandemics. Our low-cost miniaturized disposable molecular diagnostic system will allow for patient testing virtually anywhere, with laboratory quality performance, within a few minutes. The platform will enable rapid detection of Covid-19 infections on-site in a multitude of settings including drive-through testing centres, physician offices, on-site tests as well as hospitals and quarantine centres. First demonstrators of the disposable molecular platform and coronavirus test will be available five months after start of project and could be provided to emergency first responders and public health authorities. The platform is powered by a next-generation nucleic acid amplification technology called Pulse Controlled Amplification (PCA®), which enables sample-to-answer workflows in 15 minutes or less. Our European consortium comprised on teams from Italy, Spain and Germany, is highly motivated to develop a ground-breaking diagnostic solution to help the serious crisis faced across the world due to the Covid-19 epidemic.

The core invention of PCA® is a fundamentally new approach to nucleic acid amplification - heating only a fraction of the reaction through small-scale conductor that are directly embedded in the reaction, rather than integrated into an instrument. Rapid energy pulses heat the conductors selectively and cool off nearly instantaneously through passive diffusion of heat into the surrounding solution. Through this elegant method, several required temperature changes for the nucleic acid amplification can be achieved every second, which leads to a reduction of the overall amplification process by a factor of up to 10. By suitable dimensioning, less than one thousandth of the amplification solution can be heated in each pulse step, so that the reaction solution itself serves as a cooling reservoir.

A disposable platform for carrying out a molecular test based on PCA® technology is currently being developed to detect infectious diseases. The disposable instrument can be produced for a few Euros at large scale and allows patients to be tested on-site or in any doctor's office. This avoids not only complex logistics of samples to centralized high-throughput laboratories but brings the test truly to the patient. As patients can be sampled and tested on-site even the complexity of inactivating their samples (which is a challenge to subsequent diagnostics) can be simplified. Furthermore, drive through and on-site testing can avoid spreading the disease in crowded hospitals or doctor's offices but rapidly gives clarity to the patients. Unlike all existing POCT solutions, which require instruments worth at least several thousands of Euros our disposable instrument does not require any investment and can be rolled out to many places and environments that could not afford expensive equipment so far (e.g. a general practitioner's office). In view of the current coronavirus outbreak, a complementary Covid-19 assay will be implemented on the disposable device and the first prototypes will be provided for testing onsite five months after start of this project. An extremely affordable, powerful testing platform will be provided bringing the power of molecular diagnostics (sensitivity, specificity, limit of detection) to settings that were not amenable for molecular diagnostics so far such as doctor's offices, airports, drive through testing facilities and even directly with the patients at home.

A considerable number of resistance markers have already been identified by researchers world-wide, and INMI is one of the drivers of these activities. INMI will continue to characterize new and emerging mutations of COVID-19. These results will be directly translated into the design of the COVID-19 assays, where the proprietary PCA® confers the advantage that the targeted conserved sequence regions can be much shorter than when targeted with traditional qPCR assays. GNA is already working on the concept for the sample workflow including lysis, target extraction and assay integration. A direct-PCA based workflow will be established on laboratory equipment, predominantly using the Pharos Micro. The Pharos Micro will also be the instrument for the development of the assays, testing of primers, markers, and probes. chemical and enzymatic lysis and a bind-wash based DNA-extraction will be implemented. We will use its established process of for the assay integration in the disposable PCA® chip including freeze drying of the reagents accompanied by storage tests using the 8-well chip of the Pharos Micro and in parallel the transfer and verification of the assay to the disposable PCA® chip for the disposable molecular platform.

The INMI Lazzaro Spallanzani National Institute for Infectious Diseases and the BMI Bundeswehr have both access to numerous human samples and data regarding Covid-19 cases in Germany and Italy, which have been two hotspots in Europe and epicentres of the pandemic in the world. The samples are readily available for testing and validation of the disposable device as well as for further assay development.

The IMB has fully equipped stationary and deployable laboratory capacities for research and development in the field of medical bio-protection. This includes departments for virology, bacteriology, toxicology, special diagnostic services and a BSL-3 laboratory. For research and test validation purposes IMB harbors Europe's largest BSL-3 strain collection. IMB comprises furthermore a microbial genomics group which is equipped with cutting edge next generation sequencing technologies. Two specialized groups at the IMB have rapidly deployable outbreak diagnostics as main focus: a department dedicated to development and validation of novel methods for diagnostics and department for medical Bio-Reconnaissance and Verification. The Technology development department has amongst others the capacity of developing, validating and small batch production of immuno- and nucleic acid lateral flow assays. The department for medical Bio-Reconnaissance and Verification comprises the rapidly deployable laboratory equipment described elsewhere (Wölfel et al. 2015). Moreover, this department has sample expertise and is capable of sampling and investigating biological incidents using personal protective equipment and dedicated sampling equipment. Finally, the IMB has dedicated field laboratory training set-ups and provides national and international trainings for biological sampling and investigation.

INMI will focus on the validation of the device in a clinical and/or hospital setting. IMB will focus on workflow optimization and later validation for a field site environment (e.g. high throughput testing at a drive through testing facility).

The overarching goal of this clinical study by INM is the validation of the newly developed devices for case confirmation of COVID-19. The study envisages the collection of upper and lower respiratory tract samples from respiratory syndromes' infected patients, including COVID-19 cases. To reach this goal we plan to collect samples from acutely infected patients. The laboratory confirmation of SARS-CoV2 and other respiratory infections will depend on respiratory specimen collected for gold standard molecular testing that will be part of the diagnostic algorithm in the frame of patients' care. The specimens will be stored and used to evaluate the performance of newly developed Point of Care Tests (POCs).

Samples from infected patients will be collected primarily for diagnostic purposes and non-invasive respiratory samples (i.e. naso-pharyngeal swabs) will be the preferential tool while more invasive specimens (i.e. sputum, broncho-alveolar-lavage, broncho-aspirates) only collected depending on clinical advice. The target population eligible for enrolment includes suspected and confirmed SARS-CoV2 cases, based on definitions by the ECDC and WHO. Patients will be enrolled after epidemiological and/or clinical suspect of infectious respiratory syndromes including SARS-CoV-2 infection. From the end of January 2020 about 8000 respiratory samples have been screened for SARS-CoV2 at INMI and more than 400 patients have already been diagnosed by laboratory molecular tests. The overall participants (suspect and confirmed cases) will be around 300 patients. This will be complemented by anonymised body fluid samples spiked with pathogens isolates (over 300). In order to properly evaluate the performance of diagnostic tests we will collect over 300 clinical specimens and over 300 samples spiked with pathogens' isolates.

The data collected through the study can be useful to anyone who collects or compiles certain statistics regarding the Covid19 epidemic.

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable

The following FAIR methods to make DECISIONS's data "findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable" apply to the above Dataset DS_DECISION. The deliverables associated to the development of the instrument itself are declared "confidential" in the Grant Agreement. Thus, these data will not be shared with public or with the third parties without proper licensing and other IPR measures (ex. Non-disclosure Agreement). If the Consortium determines that some parts such data can be made publicly available, then they will comply with the provisions described in this section.

Search keywords	Example keywords (will be modified with the project advancement): Covid19, molecular diagnostics, PCR, polymerase chain reaction, E gene, pulse controlled amplification, handheld device, portable
Naming conventions	Files and folders at data repositories will be versioned and structured by using a name convention consisting of project name, dataset name and ID

2.2 Making data openly accessible

Results of the project will be disclosed in patents and papers according to the rules to be set out in a Consortium Agreement. This DMP is based upon H2020 requirements, comprising the FAIR principle (data must be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable). Data sharing, dissemination, and publishing shall be coordinated with the PC and the innovation management task, as patenting shall be considered before publishing (but not hinder publishing without reason). In the following section, details on the datasets identified in DECISION are given. They will be updated as data are produced in the project.

Data set reference and name	DS_DECISION
Purpose and relation to the objectives of the project	The datasets include information on the performance of diagnostic tests looking for specific target genes in collected clinical specimens and samples spiked with pathogens' isolates. The data collected through the study can be useful to anyone who collects or compiles certain statistics regarding the Corona virus.
Data types	Documents and images
Estimated date of when the data will be ready for sharing	31.05.2023
File formats	Documents and images: All common electronic document formats (.docx, .pdf, .tex, etc.)
Reuse of existing data	Processed and aggregated data may be shared by partners in case it is decided, that the data may be useful for the advancement of the project
Data production methods	The dataset will be generated by evaluating the performance of the diagnostic tests using collected clinical specimens and samples spiked with pathogens' isolates.
Expected size of the data	To be determined
Data utility	The collected dataset will be used for verification and validation of the diagnostic tests using the various stages of development of the diagnostic devices.
Potential for reuse	In addition to the project itself, the dataset will be useful for other research groups working on related subjects in the area of molecular diagnostics for Covid19.
Diffusion principles	The dataset generated will be shared among project partners through private cloud-based file sharing platforms as well as Zenodo
Data openly available	The DECISION project datasets will be first stored and organized in a database by the data owners (personal computer, or on the institutional secure server). Some datasets, for which the Consortium declares no confidentiality or IPR issues, will also be stored in Zenodo.
Tools to read or reuse data	Most data are produced in common electronic document/data/image formats (.docx, .pdf, .tex, .jpg, .eps, ASCII etc.) that do not require specific software.
Ways to make data available	Data objects will be deposited in Zenodo. Open access to data files provided over standard protocols such as HTTP. Use and reuse of data permitted.

Data and publication repository	For preservation and sharing of internal data and datasets, DECISION will use: Individual researchers data storage media Partner's individual institutions' secure data repositories Project website's private section Dedicated collaborative data/file sharing (to be determined) For Open Access data and publications, DECISION will publish the open data on Zenodo
Access procedures	All data deposited on Zenodo will be accessible without restriction for public. For other data, potential users must contact the IPR team or the data owner in order to gain access. If necessary, appropriate IPR procedure (such as non-disclosure agreement) will be used.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Standards, vocabularies, or methodologies for data	Controlled vocabularies will be used in descriptive metadata fields to support consistent, accurate, and quick indexing and retrieval of relevant data. Keywords (see section 2.2) and their synonyms will be used for indexing and subject headings of the data. As controlled vocabularies change within different disciplines of Science, these keywords will be updated during the course of the project to increase the interoperability of the project's data. List of standards/vocabularies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Covid-19 - Corona - Diagnostics - PCA - PCR - Rapid testing - Molecular testing - Portable molecular diagnostics system - Nucleic acid amplification - Rapid amplification - Pulse controlled amplification - Polymerase chain reaction - Miniaturized molecular testing system
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2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The data will be made re-useable one month after the data has been generated and processed. The data may be part of a scientific publication in a appropriate peer reviewed scientific journal. The data may also be part of an article on a website of one of the consortium partners websites. The data published may be re-used for an unlimited time.

3. Allocation of resources

Costs for making data FAIR and how to cover these costs	Fees associated with the publication of scientific articles containing project's research data in scientific journals. The cost sharing, in case of multiple authors, shall be decided among the authors on a case-by-case basis. Project Website operation: to be determined; Data archiving at Zenodo is free of charge
Data manager responsible during the project	During the project data will be updated regularly as new results are submitted by partners.

Responsibilities of partners	Every partner is responsible for the data they produce. Any fee incurred for Open Access through scientific publication of the data will be the responsibility of the data owner (authors) partner(s)
Potential value of long-term preservation	To be determined

4. Data security

Provisions for data security: DECISION will use methods that emphasize easy access and extended contact and trust building among participants. The following guidelines will be followed in order to ensure the security of the data:

- Store data in at least two separate locations to avoid loss of data;
- Encrypt data if it is deemed necessary by the participating researchers;
- Limit the use of USB flash drives;
- Label files in a systematically structured way in order to ensure the coherence of the final dataset.

5. Ethical aspects

The collection of information from confirmed cases is a public health measure that do not require prior approval by an ethics committee. The collection of samples from donors and the use of residual clinical samples will start upon approval by the INMI's ethical board. Samples will be anonymized and only the information useful for the analysis (i.e. type of sample, age and gender of the healthy donor, other infections) will be annotated. An informed consent for the use of samples for research purposes will be prepared and submitted before enrolment. A waiver will be requested in the application to the Ethical Board to allow the use of those residual clinical samples collected for diagnostic purposes and for which was not possible to obtain the informed consent. Informed consent will be obtained by a trained member of the investigation team, from all cases and contacts willing to participate in the research activity before any procedure is performed. Consent for children under the legal age of consent will be obtained from a parent or legal guardian. Each participant will be informed that participation in the investigation is voluntary and that s/he is free to withdraw, without justification, from the investigation at any time without consequences and without affecting professional responsibilities. Informed consent will seek approval to collect body fluids and epidemiological data for the intended purpose of this investigation, that samples may be shipped outside of the institution for additional testing and that samples may be used for future research purposes. This investigation poses minimal risk to participants, involving the collection of non-invasive specimens. The direct benefit to the participant is the possibility for early detection of SARS-CoV-2 infection which would allow for appropriate monitoring. The primary benefit of the study is that samples and data collected will guide the development of rapid and easy to handle tests with the potential to shorten the time-around for a diagnosis and management of infected. Participant confidentiality will be maintained throughout the investigation. All subjects who participate in the investigation, and therefore the samples derived from these individuals, will be assigned a study identification number by the investigation team for the labelling of questionnaires and clinical specimens. The link of this identification number to individuals will be maintained by the investigation team and the Ministry of Health (or equivalent) and will not be disclosed elsewhere. If the data is shared by the implementing organization to WHO or any agency or institution providing support for data analysis, data shared will include only the study identification number and not any personally identifiable information. Article 45 of the IHR (2005) describes the "treatment of personal data".¹¹ Person identifiable data collected under the IHR should be kept confidential and processed anonymously, as required by national law. However, such data may be disclosed for assessments and management of public health risks, provided the data are processed fairly and lawfully.

Scientific advice / protocol assistance:

In the frame of a project on the response and pathogenesis of emerging infections, the Ethical Committee at INMI approved the collection of samples from patients affected by emerging pathogens and their follow-up. The inclusion of SARS-CoV2 cases in the study will be communicated at the local committee who reunite every month for approval of submitted ethical proposal.

6. Other issues

No other issues at this moment.

